

The Role of AI Enablers in Overcoming Impairments in 6G Networks

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Abstract—The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the 6G architecture, referred to as AI-native 6G architecture, signifies a transformative era for communication technology. Nevertheless, practical implementation encounters challenges including architectural complexities, data quality concerns, and operational difficulties in managing machine learning models, allocating resources, and implementing intent-based management. In this paper, we present a comprehensive approach to address these challenges in emerging 6G networks through AI. Our approach involves two steps: first, we identify impairments hindering progress, analyzing the importance of addressing operational challenges in Machine Learning Operations (MLOps), 6G evolution, and democratizing AI, while addressing interoperability issues and complexities in the translation of business intents into network configurations. Upon the analysis, we highlight AI enablers—architectural enhancements, MLOps, Data Operations (DataOps), AI as a Service (AIaaS), and intent-based management—as essential solutions for practical AI implementation in 6G networks. We conclude by stating that architectural improvements prioritize privacy, security, and data accuracy, while MLOps and DataOps optimize the management of the AI life cycle. Privacy-aware data collection and training employ federated learning and split learning, and AIaaS streamlines AI access, and intent based management with integrated AI enhances decision-making through advanced algorithms.

Index Terms—6G, AI-native, AI enablers, MLOps, DataOps, AIaaS, Intent-based management, Privacy, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the 6G architecture marks a paradigm shift, AI-native 6G architecture [1], promising dynamic intelligence for communication technology [2]. The real-time optimization capabilities of AI empower 6G networks to efficiently allocate resources, predict potential issues, and adapt seamlessly to evolving demands. This level of adaptability not only ensures peak performance but also lays the groundwork for autonomous systems that can self-optimize in response to the diverse and dynamic needs of our digitally interconnected world. Moreover, the collaboration of AI and 6G provides enhanced resource allocation algorithms, learning-based adaptation, automated network configuration, intelligent load balancing, adaptive quality of service (QoS) and optimized energy consumption acknowledging a new era, reshaping communication technology for a more connected and intelligent future.

While AI holds the potential to enhance various aspects, it is not without its current limitations [3], [4]. The practical implementation of AI encounters challenges in 6G integration, including architectural complexities, data limitations, and operational hurdles. Robust frameworks and effective protocols are crucial, especially for privacy-preserving learning. Stringent AI regulations complicate dataset sharing externally, demanding continuous monitoring and privacy techniques. Operational challenges in Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) [5] further complicate efficient training and inference, while 6G evolution emphasizes resource allocation and interoperability. Democratizing AI encounters interoperability challenges [6], necessitating standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and trust for transparent outcomes. Translation of business intents into network configurations faces challenges in balancing simplicity and complexity, addressing heterogeneity and conflicting policies [7], ensuring compatibility, and requiring efficient algorithms for real-time monitoring [8].

Practical implementation of AI brings challenges along, yet concurrently, AI enablers play a crucial role in facilitating the practical implementation of AI, offering solutions to overcome the aforementioned challenges. AI enablers, including architectural enhancements, MLOps [9], Data Operations (DataOps) [10], AI as a Service (AIaaS) [11], and intent-based management [12], play a vital role in overcoming challenges for practical AI implementation in 6G networks. Architectural improvements address privacy, security, and data accuracy in cooperative learning, while MLOps and DataOps optimize AI lifecycle management through continuous monitoring and proactive updates. Privacy-aware data collection uses techniques like federated learning, and AIaaS simplifies access to AI capabilities. Additionally, integrating AI with intent-based management enhances decision-making processes using advanced algorithms [13], [14] and [15], streamlining network structures and operations.

This paper aims to provide a unified and holistic view of how AI can assist overcoming the architectural impairments in the upcoming 6G networks following a two-step approach. First, the impairments hindering progress are identified. Grounded on this analysis, AI enablers are introduced and discussed to enable progress. The rest of the paper is

organized as follows. Section II presents impairments hindering the progress. Section III provides an overview of the AI enablers that enable the progress. Concluding remarks and future directions are given in Section IV.

II. IMPAIRMENTS HINDERING PROGRESS

A. Architectural and Protocol Complexities

Architectural means and protocols play a pivotal role in facilitating the integration of AI technologies within the framework of 6G networks. To fully capitalize on the potential of AI within this context, it becomes imperative to establish a robust architectural framework and implement appropriate protocols. For example, in cooperative learning, a Machine Learning (ML)-based cooperative intelligence technique, the 6G network nodes need to cooperate and coordinate through sharing data and AI models while preserving user privacy. Therefore, there is a need to introduce architectural and protocol improvements concerning how data and models can be shared in a privacy-preserving manner and how to enable coordination between nodes. This requires enhancing existing procedures where possible and introducing novel discovery and signaling procedures for capability exchange among cooperative cellular nodes. In particular, to ensure that data and model privacy are protected, it is essential to have clear policies and procedures in place that define who has access to the data, how it is collected and how it is stored and shared. Moreover, to meet individual needs and relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI), such as communication and computation latency, improved privacy, and data accuracy, the control architecture needs to be carefully designed. In addition to these, the AI-native architecture needs to be optimized to minimize end-to-end energy consumption. The architectural components need to be designed in a self-sufficient manner, minimizing inter-component dependencies and data transfer between the components. Moreover, redundant functionalities should be avoided as much as possible while providing a robust and reliable structure.

B. Data Limitations and Quality:

As 6G networks evolve, strict AI regulations pose challenges in sharing privacy-sensitive datasets. This reluctance is due to varying privacy levels, dataset heterogeneity, and differences in system resources and model architectures.

The increasing strictness of AI regulations, aimed at ensuring trustworthiness, poses challenges in sharing datasets externally, discouraging the sharing of privacy-sensitive datasets collected locally. This hesitancy is fueled by variations in privacy levels within local datasets, where certain attributes are highly sensitive. Consequently, external access to such privacy-sensitive datasets is restricted. Datasets sourced from different entities may exhibit heterogeneity in terms of quality, data types, and distribution across decentralized nodes, contributing to data heterogeneity. Variations in computation and communication resources at different entity locations, termed system heterogeneity, further complicate data management and

differences in ML model architecture and types across entities introduce model heterogeneity.

On the other hand, the emergence of heterogeneous networks and distributed data applications necessitates advanced approaches such as distributed ML, e.g., federated learning and split learning for decentralized decision-making. To enable distributed ML in cellular nodes, there is a requirement for data and model exchange between the cellular network and user equipment (UE). However, learning from valuable UE data is impeded by the privacy sensitivity of the data. Overcoming this challenge involves introducing privacy-preserving techniques for data collection, and striking a balance between computation overhead, energy consumption [16], and model/learning efficiency. Therefore, addressing these issues requires a holistic approach that encompasses dataset sharing, privacy preservation, and the efficient exchange of data and models.

C. Operational Challenges in MLOps

In the realm of ML model operations, the focus is on sustaining efficient model training and inference, with the overarching goals of minimizing resource consumption and maximizing efficacy. However, challenges arise when dealing with datasets that cannot be moved from their local collection points due to sensitivity or regulatory constraints. To tackle this, distributed ML techniques come into play, allowing models to be trained locally and then shared through model parameter exchange.

The decision to employ distributed learning is often driven by concerns related to privacy, data regulations, and computational overhead. This approach introduces the need for additional KPIs to evaluate and maintain efficient MLOps. The defined KPIs encompass aspects like compute, model efficacy, communication, energy efficiency, and privacy. Striking a balance between these KPIs becomes crucial, dependent on the specific task, such as intent, and the available resources.

When extending distributed ML to cellular nodes, the exchange of data and models between the cellular network and UE becomes crucial. This introduces new challenges in managing data (DataOps) and ML models (MLOps), such as incorporating privacy-preserving aggregation functions into the 6G architecture and implementing coordination mechanisms to keep models and data up to date and synchronized among cellular nodes, impacting network architecture and protocols.

D. Resource Allocation and Interoperability Challenges

With the journey toward 6G, the network is envisioned to transform into an AI-native platform, employing AI internally while also making its AI capabilities available to support diverse applications. However, seamless integration of AI capabilities into the 6G network is still to be realized, as it is currently limited by a few interoperability challenges. As depicted in Fig. 1, first, common, if not standardized, APIs are required to unify access and exposure to AI services, including data collection and transfer, data processing, ML model training and inference, in a way that they can be

consumed by several stakeholders through common operations. In addition, trust among AI service providers and consumers needs to be established systematically to unlock AI capabilities exchange across the involved stakeholders while facilitating the introduction of security and privacy at the AI level as key trust enablers. Moreover, explainable AI solutions need to be pervasively adopted and integrated to make AI outputs and predictions understandable and interpretable for the stakeholders consuming the services, thus maximizing the impact of AI usage.

Beyond the challenges of integrating AI into 6G networks, the allocation of resources in the AI service life cycle presents a new multifaceted challenge due to the diverse and potentially limited nature of resources. This encompasses communication and storage resources essential for data collection, transfer, and caching, as well as computing and communication resources crucial for distributed model training and inference. Furthermore, new QoS requirements emerge to be considered during resource allocation, different from the conventional network-related ones, e.g., data quality, training latency, and inference accuracy. Consequently, real-time optimization problems of high complexity arise, demanding solutions that strike a delicate balance between computational complexity, communication, interference, energy consumption, and accuracy [17].

Fig. 1. AIaaS interoperability context.

E. Intent-Based Management Translation Challenges

In light of the broader vision for automating and streamlining network administration, intent-based management brings its challenges into focus. The transition from conventional network management to intent-based approaches involves addressing complexities in translating high-level business intents into precise and implementable network configurations. Striking a balance between the simplicity of expressing intents and the complexity of executing them within the network infrastructure demands an important understanding of business requirements and technical intricacies. At the same time, the real-world networking environment is characterized by heterogeneity and complexity, featuring various types of devices, technologies, and vendors. This diversity may give rise to contradictory policies that need resolution within the same or

even between different network domains. Optimizing the performance of a specific type of device or technology may conflict with another intent emphasizing cost reduction or energy efficiency across the network. Sophisticated algorithms and intelligent systems are required to secure coherent resource allocation and prioritization that align with the organization's ultimate goals. Moreover, given the integration of intent-based solutions into current infrastructures, it is imperative to ensure compatibility and uphold existing security protocols. Subsequently, real-time network monitoring (e.g., performance metrics, traffic patterns) and reconfiguration play a critical role in detecting anomalies or deviations from the established intents. Finally, all employed algorithms must be efficient and scalable under the high volume of devices, policies, and configurations.

III. ENABLING PROGRESS: THE ROLE OF AI ENABLERS

A. Architectural Enhancements

Data-driven architecture plays a crucial role in overcoming the challenges of AI deployment and its integration into 6G network systems. It offers architectural components, interfaces, and protocols that facilitate data collection and exchange between various distributed endpoints across heterogeneous domains, such as Core, RAN, and UE. Additionally, it supports ML model training, deployment, inference, and performance monitoring, contributing to AI-enabled 6G systems. Specifically, data-driven architectures include automated data generation and collection from relevant sources based on the service or use case through dedicated interfaces at periodic intervals and/or on-demand. This approach ensures data accuracy and freshness. The collected data is then aggregated, processed, and stored in dedicated functions or repositories, making it available for data analytics or training ML models.

Furthermore, these architectural frameworks provide communication interfaces and protocols for enabling distributed cooperative model training. This includes methodologies like Federated Learning or Split Learning, where the model training task involves multiple distributed training instances. Once the model is trained and deployed on inference instances, ML model performance can be monitored across all deployed instances in a distributed manner. Regular performance data collection and analysis help detect and mitigate performance degradation efficiently, allowing for the propagation of mitigation actions across all distributed inference instances.

The general model for cooperative learning involves network nodes (UEs, base stations) participating in learning to achieve a common task, as depicted in Fig. 2. Privacy-aware data classification determines whether UE data is shared partially, totally, or kept locally based on privacy sensitivity. Privacy-preserving measures are implemented for data and model sharing, with careful consideration of privacy-utility trade-offs. For instance, UE1 and UE2, possessing privacy-sensitive data, receive a trained model from the base station, which infers local privacy-sensitive data and shares only the corresponding inference. Base station 1 combines these inferences with its own data to achieve the common cooperation

Fig. 2. Cooperative Learning in 6G.

task. UE3, with data of lower privacy sensitivity, participates in cooperative learning by partially or fully sharing data or models. Base station 2 may also participate in cooperative learning. However, current cooperative learning operates at the application level, lacking tailored network architecture, protocols, and procedures specific to its stringent requirements on privacy/security and data accuracy. Therefore, introducing corresponding architectural changes and modifications to network protocols and procedures is necessary to address these specifics.

B. Empowered MLOps and DataOps

Within the landscape of AI-native 6G, DataOps and MLOps are essential in addressing the challenges of deploying AI and integrating it seamlessly into 6G network systems by enabling a more efficient zero-touch end-to-end ML model life cycle management that fully automates data generation, collection, processing, and updates, as well as trains, monitors, and updates ML models. Implementing autonomous control loops for specific tasks enhances the quality and efficiency of ML models. Consequently, continuous monitoring of the model's performance and environmental changes facilitates improvements, triggering new data collection or generation, and model re-training or updates upon detecting changes in model performance. Additionally, proactive measures are taken by detecting or predicting events in advance and triggering actions to prevent model performance degradation.

Considering dependencies between data, models, and inter-model relationships (e.g., Transfer Learning, Continual Learning, Split Learning, or training models based on data from a Digital Twin instead of a real deployment) enhances the efficiency of model life cycle management. Detecting model performance degradation or significant changes in the environment or data source can prompt automated updates in related models, helping mitigate the propagation of degradation or even prevent it. Applied to 6G networks, MLOps and DataOps will play a crucial role in automating and optimizing network and service management. These processes involve providing, continuously monitoring, and maintaining the performance of ML models for tasks such as resource allocation optimization,

Fig. 3. Privacy-preserving architecture for data collection, learning, and analytics.

fault prediction, mitigation, and avoidance, or optimizing network service management.

Private federated learning and private data aggregation enable privacy-preserving learning on user data. Privacy is preserved by combining differential privacy with secure aggregation techniques in such a way that reliable statistical information of aggregated data can still be learned without revealing personally identifiable information. When placed in the future cellular context, aggregated data originating from several UEs is collected from a defined sampling area and over a defined sampling time window. The data shared with the network does not capture individual private data but could consist of statistical measures (mean, variance, distribution, etc.) and/or analytical insights of the users in the network. The size of aggregated data samples should be sufficiently large not to reveal personal information while providing adequate privacy-utility trade-offs.

The privacy-preserving architecture for data collection, learning, and analytics is illustrated in Fig. 3. The main architectural component is the UE aggregation unit, which performs privacy-preserving data aggregation. It uses secure aggregation techniques and/or data anonymization to collect user data and should not contain any confidential information about a specific user. Another architectural component would be the data-driven network control unit, an entity on the network side that configures the base station by performing automation, optimization, and intelligence services based on both network and UE data. UE-collected data (contextual data, measurements) is shared by the UE aggregator with the data-driven network control unit and can be used by the network to improve its control and decisions. The exact implementation of the aggregation mechanism and the servers split/deployment can be agreed upon between UE and network vendors to enable privacy-preserving coordination.

Privacy-preserving cryptographic protocols like Prio [18], currently being standardized in the IETF Privacy Preserving Measurement Workgroup [19], can be used. Also, depending on the level of privacy of data, different training mechanisms can be applied. For example, in the case of privacy-sensitive

Fig. 4. Example illustration of cross-network function training and model generalization via joint optimization for multiple use cases in a multi-headed, multi-tailed split learning setting.

UE data, a model is trained in the UE and shared with the network using private federated learning.

Moreover, in some cases the data attributes on distributed nodes may be vertically split meaning that they may not have the same data features, especially when they are obtained from different layers in the communication stack (Physical, MAC, IP or Application). The training then can be enabled via vertical federated learning using Split Learning [20]. This assists cross-network function training and inference, model generalization to multiple tasks, and offloading some of the model layers from one computation node to another enable efficiency with respect to privacy, computation, storage, and communication capacity requirements. Fig. 4 illustrates the above cases as follows: The individual learnings obtained by training on individual performance measurement datasets collected at different network functions such as gNB, user plane function (UPF), and output consumers, e.g., application clients or servers are combined to construct one single global ML model. This enables joint training for a task, such as video bit rate or delay estimation in a video service, without sharing raw datasets. Each network entity trains part of the single model and shares the learnings between each other over the exchange of model outputs, i.e., activations and model gradients iteratively. The jointly learned output of a generalization node can then be reused for multiple tasks, such as video bit rate and video delay estimation, reducing the computation and communication requirements. Moreover, in the case where the computation availability at the network functions is scarce, these computation tasks can be offloaded to more available compute entities, potentially reducing the computation and energy overhead on limited devices.

C. AIaaS for Accessibility

Toward 6G, the network envisions a shift towards becoming an AI-native platform, internally leveraging AI and extending its AI capabilities to support diverse applications. Coined as AIaaS, this concept positions the network as an AIaaS provider, offering readily available AI models, datasets, algorithms, and tools accessible to applications through APIs for discovering, exploring, and consuming AI capabilities to address their specific heterogeneous needs. The primary advantage of AIaaS lies in enabling applications to harness

AI functionalities without the necessity for application developers to construct and manage their own AI infrastructure. This transformative evolution transforms the network into a platform fostering innovation across a spectrum of use cases [11].

The AIaaS framework aims to hide the complexity of deploying AI services and models across the extreme-edge, edge, and cloud continuum. It achieves this by integrating MLOps tools and mechanisms to automate models' management and Software Development Operations (DevOps) routines. Additionally, AIaaS incorporates API orchestration logic to expose AI capabilities in the form of tailored services and models, depending on the specific use cases to be supported [11]. These services and models come with constraints in terms of performance, execution, and deployment.

In practice, AIaaS has the potential to democratize access to and use of AI capabilities for a variety of stakeholders [6]. It serves as a key facilitator for AI and data monetization, enabling new business propositions and the realization of AI-driven vertical services and network applications.

D. Intent-Based Management with AI

Intent-based management refers to a sophisticated approach that elevates the orchestration of diverse AI components within a data-driven framework. This methodology empowers the seamless adaptation of resources in response to fluctuating workloads, thereby optimizing the overall performance of AI-driven processes in alignment with their intended objectives. By harnessing the capabilities of intent-based management, the data-driven architecture gains heightened agility, responsiveness, and intelligence. This strategic integration results in more effective and adaptive AI implementations, where the dynamic allocation of resources and real-time adjustments align the AI system with its goals, fostering a robust and efficient operational environment.

Moreover, the combination of AI and intent-based management can lead to faster, more accurate, and scalable decision-making processes and network structures. Closed-loop network automation involves several critical stages, including intent translation, policy generation, conflict detection, network configuration, monitoring, and adaptation. AI can significantly enhance the performance of each stage. Analytically, each stage entails solving complex optimization problems, which becomes more challenging with larger networks and more diverse system requirements. AI-driven solutions, on the contrary, enable quick exploration of a vast network state space and adaptation of the underlying network infrastructure based on a trained ML model. The trained model evolves to recognize normal patterns and anomalies in complex datasets collected during network operations. Training can be conducted offline using existing data, and the trained models can be further fine-tuned in real-time to provide timely and up-to-date decisions to the network.

In the context of intent translation, AI is applied through the utilization of Natural Language processing [13], such as Recurrent Neural Networks [14], Long Short-Term Memory

[15], and others. These powerful neural networks extract features of different services while considering the order dependence of written intents. This process accurately identifies and classifies the service intent. Additionally, Deep Evolutionary Neural Networks [14], which combine neural networks and evolutionary algorithms, prove valuable in identifying failures during network configuration and effectively handling conflicts in intents and generated policies.

IV. CONCLUSION

The synergy between AI and 6G extends beyond conventional enhancements such as enhanced resource allocation algorithms, learning-based adaptation, etc., paving the way for a more interconnected and intelligent future. Nonetheless, the practical application of this integration encounters significant hurdles, spanning from intricate architectural complexities to the constraints imposed by stringent AI regulations. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, and this paper has highlighted crucial AI enablers as solutions.

Enhanced architecture, focusing on privacy and security, along with advancements in MLOps and DataOps, optimizes AI lifecycle management. AIaaS aims to democratize AI, but requires standardized APIs and trust for interoperability. Intent-based management faces complexities, needing efficient algorithms for real-time actuation and monitoring. In the evolving 6G landscape, clear policies are crucial for navigating strict AI regulations, especially regarding privacy-sensitive datasets. Techniques like federated learning and split learning are essential for managing privacy and data challenges. MLOps and DataOps are vital for efficient AI model lifecycle management, addressing trade-off between computation and communication with adaptive compute offloading mechanisms as well as regulatory constraints on sensitive datasets. AIaaS in 6G networks aims for accessibility, scalability, and adaptability, relying on common APIs, trust, and explainable AI solutions for impact maximization. Overcoming interoperability challenges in seamless AI integration into 6G requires standardized APIs, trust mechanisms, and explainable AI solutions.

Future directions should focus on refining architectural framework, establishing standardized APIs, and enhancing interoperability to enable a seamless fusion of AI capabilities within 6G networks. Collaborative efforts are needed to address the evolving landscape of AI regulations, ensuring trustworthiness, and promoting responsible AI practices. Moreover, research in privacy-preserving techniques, federated learning, and advanced algorithms for intent-based management will further contribute to the practical implementation of AI in 6G networks. In conclusion, the paper emphasizes the need for a holistic and collaborative approach to realize the full potential of AI in shaping the future of communication technology.

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